

Impacts of Flash Flood on Ground Water Quality: Case Study of Central River Region, The Gambia

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Abstract:

Floods rank as one of the most common natural calamities, impacting the lives of millions across the globe. With ongoing population growth and expanding water and land usage, the potential for contamination and human disturbances to negatively impact water bodies continues to rise globally. This paper aims to comprehensively analyze the repercussions of floods on the groundwater quality of a region called CRR in the Gambia, during the July 2022 flood event. The focus lies on exploring the change in water quality parameters of twelve water samples from wells and

boreholes through laboratory analysis of eight parameters such as pH, turbidity, temperature, electrical conductivity, total dissolved solids, nitrate, iron, sulfate, and microbial proliferation. The laboratory analysis results of the physiochemical parameters such as turbidity, and iron exceeded the safe drinking water standards set by the World Health Organization (WHO) in about 60% of the sites and fecal coliform presence in 75 % of the samples. The other parameters varied differently across all sites. However, most of the values are observed to be more prominent at the open well than borehole. The Water Quality Index (WAWQI) score also shows that 1 site has excellent water quality, 25%, has good quality and 25% has fair quality. The rest of the sites which make up 42% of the samples, are all of poor quality and unsuitable for drinking purposes. The results provide a crucial groundwork for subsequent studies targeting the water quality in this area.

Keywords: Flood, Groundwater quality, Laboratory analyses, Water quality parameters, Water quality index.

Introduction

The integrity of water quality is vital for the health of ecosystems and human societies alike. Ensuring the availability of uncontaminated, potable water is critical for meeting basic human necessities, including hydration and hygiene, while also underpinning various economic

sectors and agricultural practices (United Nations Environment Program, 2010). No animal or plant life can exist without water. However, the availability of freshwater for human consumption is limited (Mishra, 2023), emphasizing the urgent need to ensure sufficient water resources for the ongoing existence of

both humans and ecosystems. According to the World Health Organization (WHO, 2023), universal access to clean water is not only a basic human right but also a critical step in elevating living standards globally. Without access to clean and potable water (Forde et al., 2019; Pal et al., 2014), individuals face increased risks of waterborne diseases, food contamination, and compromised ecosystem health.

However, water quality faces increasing threats from environmental stressors, with one of the most severe being flooding. During flood events, groundwater quality reduction can occur due to the transport of pollutants and the impact of flooding on groundwater recharge (Alam et al., 2021; Reza). Flooding can also disrupt abstraction from artificial reservoirs and degrade stored water quality due to turbidity and other contaminants (Alam et al., 2021; Sweya et al., 2020; Xu). Flooding may affect well fields, leading to pump failure and the ingress of chemically/microbiologically contaminated water into damaged wells (Baig et al., 2012; Reza; Silvia Barbetta). Water that is tainted with harmful microorganisms or a variety of chemical pollutants can lead to a host of human illnesses, especially prevalent in less developed nations (Baig et al., 2012; Said Qasim a et al.). These health conditions often arise from consuming contaminated food or water, or through exposure to polluted water during activities like bathing or cleaning. In Africa, it is estimated that up to 80% of diseases are associated with substandard water quality and inadequate sanitation. (Ashbolt, 2004; Lapworth et al., 2017).

Global climate change, along with human activities impacting the environment, has resulted in a notable increase in extreme rainfall occurrences in urban areas. (Qin & Lu, 2014). Observable alterations in global precipitation patterns, elevated atmospheric water vapor, glacier melting, a rise in flood occurrences (Tabari, 2020), and soil erosion become more pronounced (Pendergrass et al., 2017).

The swift expansion of urban areas in the Gambia, coupled with inadequate support for

effective waste management, has exacerbated pollution in bodies of water and poses a risk to the purity of subterranean water sources. This situation reflects the broader challenges of balancing development and environmental sustainability in rapidly growing urban environments. Flood risk remains significant in this low-altitude country, with approximately 20% of its land covered by wetlands (Rojas et al., 2017). The anticipated rise in sea levels, shallow water tables, waterlogged soils, coastal erosion, and the gradual encroachment of wetlands all contribute to the heightened flood risk in settlements within the Gambia, especially the greater Banjul Area (Hildebrand, 2013). Consequently, flooding directly impacts society through asset loss and indirectly through disruptions to goods and services, such as increased medical expenses and decreased productivity due to higher rates of disease, injury, and mortality.

The flash floods that struck the Gambia in 2022 stand out as one of the most severe incidents in nearly fifty years (Agulonye, 2023). The relentless rain and thunderstorms caused extensive damage, particularly in densely populated areas like Banjul. According to data from the Department of Water Resources, Banjul International Airport in Yundum, received a rainfall quantity of 276 mm during this period. A similar event occurred on July 31st, 1998, albeit with significantly lower rainfall recorded at 175.4 mm. Historical flood records dating back to 1948 highlight occurrences in 1988, 1999, 2002, 2010, and 2020. Indicating a concerning increase in the frequency of flash floods and climate-related incidents (Ibol, 2023). Following the initial flash floods, subsequent heavy downpours occurred almost daily, particularly on August 5th and 6th, exacerbating flooding in numerous communities and prolonging the duration of high-water levels. The Gambia National Disaster Management Agency (NDMA), reports over 43,984 casualties, of which impacts include the destruction of houses, food stock, toilet facilities, and household items, and a considerable number of lives still in jeopardy (<https://reliefweb.int/organization/ifr>

c, 2022). Among the affected population, 51% are females, including 2,846 pregnant and breastfeeding women, while children under five years old constitute 22%. Furthermore, the floods disrupted more than 392 water points and 1,200 sanitation facilities, with septic tank overflow contributing to water system contamination, thereby posing significant health hazards (https://reliefweb.int/organization/ifrc, 2022).

Hence, this research endeavors to execute an exhaustive evaluation of flooding effects on groundwater quality of the Case study following the 2022 flash flood in the Gambia, through laboratory analysis and water quality index (WQI) scores. The intent is to utilize this information to advocate for essential measures for site remediation. Additionally, the findings can serve as a valuable planning tool for the development and formulation of water management and safety plans. Can also provide insights for future research endeavors with similar objectives.

Description of Study Area

The Gambia, a slender country situated along the Western Coast of Africa, is characterized by its small and elongated shape, bordered by Senegal. It lies between longitude 13 and 16

West and within latitude 13 North (NEA 2010). It encompasses approximately 11,300 sq. km, with a length of about 400 km and a variable width ranging from 24 to 50 km. According to the National Population Census (GBOS, 2013) the country has an estimated population of 2 million people, experiencing a population growth rate of 2.8% per annum.

Situated between the Tropic of Cancer and the Equator, the country is subject to intense sunlight and high temperatures throughout most of the year (NAPA, 2007), the mean temperature of the Gambia has been 25 degrees Celsius with a daily temperature consistently increasing since 1965. Functioning as a Sahelian state with a sub-tropical climate, the Gambia's weather is influenced by the West African Monsoon (WAM) wind system, driven by thermal differences between land and sea with the release of heat into the atmosphere(Cornforth, 2013) The country experiences a short rainy season from June to October and a prolonged dry season from November to May, with an average annual rainfall of 900 mm(Headquarters, 2014). Climate change effects have rendered the rainy season more unpredictable, adversely affecting water security, crops, and daily life in general(Healey, 2014).

Figure 1. The Location of the Gambia with the Study Region in Yellow Colour

The study area (figure 1) is located in one of the six regions in the Gambia called the Central River Region. The region is divided into north and south by the river Gambia, featuring extensive freshwater floodplains on either side of the river. The area is characterized by good soil structure and fertility with dense vegetative cover compared to the rest of the country especially the Northern part (Bah et al., 2019). They are notable for cruising boats for river transportation, livestock and rice production, and other agricultural land uses. According to the 2013 census, the area is inhabited by 226,018 people with the majority depending on agriculture.(Statistic, 2013).The main source of drinking water for this region is groundwater from wells or boreholes. Considering the closeness of the river to the settlement, combined with the agricultural activities, and open waste disposal, the place is very prone to water pollution and contamination during flooding.

Materials and Methods

The study comprises both field and laboratory work. The field activities involved sample collection from wells and boreholes within the study area to capture the impact of a heavy flash flood on groundwater quality. Considering the geographical distribution, environmental factors, and some sanitary issues. The site coordinates were recorded using geographical position systems (GPS)

Sample Collection

Samples were systematically collected from all sites using sterilized and calibrated equipment. Carefully collected in clean polyethylene 1-liter bottles, wrapped in foil, and packed in ice boxes to preserve their integrity, samples are then transported to the water quality laboratory for further analysis. The eight selected parameters for this analysis are pH, conductivity, total dissolved solids, turbidity, nitrate, sulfate, iron, and fecal coliform.

Table 1. Water Sampling Sites' Location with Corresponding GPS Coordinates

Site nos.	Description	Latitude (N)	Longitude(W)
1	Borehole	13.542668	14.785430
2	Shallow open well	13.235678	16.345787
3	Shallow open well	13.68670	14.879802
4	Borehole	13.325844	16.272015
5	Borehole	13.351162	15.192200
6	Shallow open well	13.471150	15.841821
7	Shallow open well	13.69271	15.325164
8	Borehole	13.465754	14.595473
9	Shallow open well	13.414685	14.524754
10	Shallow open well	13.305533	14.505311
11	Deep protected well	13.385839	15.253477
12	Deep protected well	13.586306	15.042495

Analyses

On-site measurements of some parameters, which include pH, conductivity (uS/cm), and total dissolved solids (mg/l) were done using the YSI Pro Plus in-situ water quality probe and turbidity using the HACH 2100 turbidity meter. The rest of the parameters were analyzed at the lab using a spectrophotometer for the chemical

analysis and an incubator for the microbiology. The fecal coliform count was done using the filtration technique. Nitrate levels were determined using the Nitra Ver 5 reagent with the cadmium reduction method. The Ferro Ver Iron Reagent was employed for the colorimetric determination of iron levels, while the turbidimetric method was utilized for sulfate analysis. Data quality was ensured through blank

measurements, spiked, and duplicate samples.

Statistical analysis is done using Excel 2019 software, for average, minimum, maximum, and standard deviations of the data for each parameter and compared with WHO standards for drinking water. WQI is calculated and described using the method by Brown et al. (1972) method

Water Quality Index

The water quality index (WQI) adopted for this study is the Weight Arithmetic Water Quality Index method by Brown et al. (1972). This method was chosen because it is a significant metric for evaluating water purity and it condenses complex data into a single, straightforward data. reflecting the overall condition of the water. The index consists of key steps that include; choosing relevant parameters, converting data to a uniform scale, assigning importance weights to each parameter, and combining the individual scores into a total index value. The index scores are calculated using the following equations:

$$WQI = \frac{\sum W_n Q_n}{\sum W_n} \quad (1)$$

The quality rating scale (Q_n) sub-index value is calculated by:

$$Q_n = \frac{[(v_n - v_o)]}{[s_n - v_o]} * 100 \quad (2)$$

Where v_n is the mean concentration of the n^{th} parameters in the analyzed water sample results, s_n is the desirable standard value of the n^{th} parameters and v_o is the actual value of the parameters in pure water. (generally, v_o is (0) for all parameters except PH which is calculated as;

$$Q_{pH} = \frac{[(V_{pH} - 7)]}{[(8.5 - 7)]} * 100$$

W_n is the unit weight of each parameter summed up to one and is calculated as follows

$$w_n = \frac{k}{s_n} \quad (3)$$

Where K is the proportionality constant and is calculated by the following equation

$$K = \frac{2}{\frac{1}{s_1} + \frac{1}{s_2} + \frac{1}{s_3} + \dots + \frac{1}{s_n}} = \frac{1}{\sum \frac{1}{s_n}} \quad (4)$$

The rating scale and assessment criteria of the index score as Brown et al. (1972) is shown in the table below.

Table 2. Water Quality Index (WQI) Criteria

Water Quality Index Value (WQI)	Description
0-25	Excellent
26 - 50	Good water quality
51 -75	Fair water quality
76 - 100	poor water quality
101-150	Very poor water quality
> 150	Unfit for drinking purposes

Results and Discussion

Water Quality Index Scores

The results from the WQI analyses of the physicochemical parameters score obtained showed only site number 1, has excellent water quality. Site numbers 4, 8, and 11 are of good quality. Site numbers 5, 6, and 12 score fair water quality. The rest of the sites, which make up 42% of the samples are of either poor or very poor quality. Making them unfit for consumption and any domestic use before proper treatment. Thus, indicating the critical need for water treatment after flooded events. The table below shows the scores of the WQI and description according to Brown et al., (1972).

Table 3. Assessment of Groundwater Quality Status and Possible Usage

Sampling Location	Site Number	WQI scores	Remark	Possible usage
Inside Compound (Borehole)	Site 1	24	Excellent water quality	Drinking, irrigation, industrial
Inside Garden (Shallow open well)	Site 2	246	Unsuitable for drinking	Needs to be treated before any use
Inside garden (Shallow open well)	Site 3	120	Very poor water quality	Restricted used for irrigation only
Inside compound (Borehole)	Site 4	45	Good water quality	Domestic, irrigation, Industrial
Inside Garden (Borehole)	Site 5	72	Fair water quality	Irrigation and Industrial
Inside comp. (Shallow open well)	Site 6	75	Fair water quality	Irrigation and Industrial
Inside garden (Shallow open well)	Site 7	187	Unsuitable for drinking	Needs to be treated before any use
Inside compound (Borehole)	Site 8	44	Good water quality	Domestic, irrigation, Industrial
Inside compound (Shallow open well)	Site 9	78	poor water quality	irrigation
Inside garden (Shallow open well)	Site 10	233	Unsuitable for drinking	Needs to be treated before any use
Inside comp. (Deep protected well)	Site 11	49	Good water quality	Needs to be treated before any use
Inside garden (Deep protected well)	Site 12	69	Fair water quality	Irrigation and Industrial

Water Quality Parameters Variation

Comprehending the quality of drinking water is crucial as it directly impacts its suitability for consumption. The standards used to investigate water quality are regulations established to ensure that water meets specific requirements, preventing health issues, diseases, technical disruptions, and aesthetic disturbances. These standards are typically defined by statements or numerical criteria. Various factors, such as climate, precipitation, geological composition, human activities, pollutants, and natural

processes, can influence water quality standards. The important parameters selected for this study include physical parameters (e.g. temperature, turbidity, conductivity, and total dissolved solution. Chemical parameters (e.g. pH, nitrate, sulfate, and total iron). Microbiological parameters (e.g. fecal coliform bacteria). The results are statistically described by (MIN, MAX, MEAN, and STDV), together with the changes in the basic physical, chemical, and microbiological characteristics it exhibits, and compared with WHO permissible limits for drinking water quality.

Table 4. Analyzed Laboratory Results of the Selected Parameters

Parameters	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
pH	6.5	6.5	6.2	5.8	5.7	6.2	5.8	6.2	6.8	6.0	5.9	6.2
EC (µS/cm)	46.3	1970	481	113.6	210.	380	700	148.6	186	949	85	100
TDS (mg/l)	22.6	976	215	54.7	90.2	200	356	62.2	88.	381	41	43.7
Turb.(mg/l)	0.1	8	5.1	0.15	2.00	4.00	5.6	1	4	6.2	2	3.0
NO ₃ -N(mg/l)	2.00	9.00	5.80	2.60	2.00	4.60	8	1.80	3.90	6.0	3.0	3.0
So ₄ ²⁻ (mg/l)	24	150	142	22	40	48	124	50	98	130	32	70
Fe ³⁺ (mg/l)	0.12	0.80	0.38	0.20	0.28	0.32	0.6	0.26	0.3	1.0	0.26	0.32
FC/100 ml	0	42.0	16.0	4.00	0.00	24	30	8.00	48	40	6	0

Table 1. Statistical Description of the Results

Parameters	MIN	MAX	MEAN	STD. Dev	WHO. GV
PH	5.7	6.8	6.16	0.38	6.5
Conductivity ($\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$)	46.3	1970	527.57	666.03	1300
TDS (mg/l)	22.6	976	252.07	328.29	100
Turbidity (NTU)	0.1	8	3.52	2.78	5
Nitrate ($\text{NO}_3\text{-N}$) mg/l	1.8	9	4.46	2.66	10
Sulphate (SO_4^{2-}) mg/l	22	150	78.71	51.27	250
Iron (mg/l)	0.12	1	0.43	0.31	0.3
FC (CFU /100 ml)	0	48	19	19.15	0

Physical Parameters

The physical qualities of water are ascertainable through the senses of touch, sight, smell, and taste. For instance, temperature is evaluated through touch, while turbidity and suspended solids are assessed visually, and taste and odor are discerned through smell (Arora, 2017).

- **Turbidity**

Turbidity is a degree of the light-transmitting properties of water. It can be influenced by human movement, rotting plant matter, algal blossoms, suspended dregs, and plant supplements. Turbidity gives an appraisal of adding up to suspended solids (TSS) concentration in water [81] and it is a vital drinking-water quality parameter and water treatment. Elevated levels of turbidity can disturb the effectiveness of ordinary water treatment strategies such as flocculation, coagulation, sedimentation, and filtration.

The turbidity records of the sample range from 0.1 to 8 (NTU) as the lowest and highest values respectively, with a mean value of 3.52 and a standard deviation of 3.28. Site numbers 2, 3, 7, and 10, which are both open shallow wells exceeded the accepted WHO permissible limits of 5NTU for drinking water. This is an indication of the effect of the flood runoff as it moves with sand, debris, and other suspensions of organic matter, entering the wells that were shallow and not protected during the flooding time and thus, increasing their turbidity level.

- **Electrical Conductivity**

Water conductivity refers to its capacity to conduct electricity due to the dissolution of solids into positively and negatively charged ions

(Arora, 2017). Conductivity measurements indicate groundwater seepage, sewage leak, variety of water body's hardness, alkalinity, and dissolved solids concentration. High conductivity in water may result from pollution sources such as agricultural runoff, urban runoff, industrial discharges, or natural processes like weathering and erosion (Subba Rao et al., 2020).

The electrical conductivity (EC), records 1970 ($\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$) at site 2, followed by 949 ($\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$) at site 10 and 700 ($\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$) at site 7 as the three highest values respectively. Site number 1 registered 46.3 ($\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$) and site number 11 registered 85 ($\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$) as the lowest values respectively. It shows a mean value of 527 and a standard deviation of 666. Apart from site number 2, all the other sites are within the acceptable permissible limits of drinking water quality standards by WHO.

- **Total dissolved solids**

This term refers to the inorganic salts and organic substances dissolved within a water solution. The presence of various dissolved minerals such as manganese, sodium, carbonate, chloride, and other cations and anions contribute to the conductivity and TDS values of water (Abood et al., 2009). High TDS levels can result in undesirable tastes and odors, impacting the palatability and acceptance of water by consumers.

The TDS value of the samples ranges from 976 mg/l as the highest to 22.6 mg/l as the lowest. With a mean value of 252 and a standard deviation of 328, all the sites are within the WHO permissible limit. Because of the linearity that relates TDS and EC; the trend observed for the EC values was also reflected in the TDS

values.

Chemical parameters

Most chemicals are of concern only following long-term exposure; however, some hazardous chemicals that occur in drinking water are of concern because of the arising effects from sequences of exposures over a short period. Which may give rise to a significant number of serious health concerns.

- pH

pH is a measure of how acidic or basic (alkaline) the water is. It is defined as the negative log of the hydrogen ion concentration of a solution. pH affects the interaction of substances in a solution and can alter the concentrations of other substances in water to a more toxic form. pH variations affect aquatic life's physiological processes and behavior (Blewett et al., 2022; Scott & Sloman, 2004), which can lead to physical damage to gills, exoskeletons, fins, or even death.

The pH values ranged from 6.8 at site 9 which is a shallow well as the highest, and 5.7 at site 5, a borehole as the lowest. It has an average mean value of 6.16 and a standard deviation of 0.38. Site number 9 with 6.8 and site numbers 1 and 2 with 6.5 are within the WHO permissible limits. All other sites were slightly acidic.

- Nitrate

Nitrates play a vital role in numerous biochemical processes and are essential for fostering plant growth, serving as a primary nutrient in fertilizers (Sinha & Tandon, 2020). However, excessive nitrate levels in aquatic environments can profoundly degrade water quality, cause eutrophication and disrupt ecosystems. (Ishak, 2012). Nitrate can infiltrate groundwater via sources such as agricultural runoff, sewage discharges, septic systems, and pesticides (Burkart & Kolpin, 1993).

The nitrates values range from 1.8 mg/l as the lowest at site number 8 and 9mg/l as the highest at site number 2. With mean values of 4.46 and standard deviation of 2.66, all the records are within the WHO permissible limits. However, the values are observed to be more prominent in

the open wells than in the borehole. Indicating the flood impact in the open shallow well rather than boreholes.

- Sulfate

Sulfate can occur naturally in water bodies due to the weathering of rocks and minerals containing sulfur (Abubakar Suleiman et al., 2021). Additionally, human activities such as mining, industrial processes, and wastewater discharges can contribute to elevated sulfate levels in water sources. A high quantity of sulfate in drinking water can be laxative and lead to diarrhea in some people (Zak et al., 2021). It also imparts a bitter taste and unpleasant odor, which can affect consumer acceptance and satisfaction (Dietrich & Burlingame, 2015).

The sulfate results records range from 22 mg/l as the lowest to 150 mg/l as the highest. With a mean of 78.71 and a standard deviation of 51.27, all the sites measured are within the range of the WHO permissible limit. There is no flood impact observed as they vary differently across all sites.

- Iron

Iron is an essential trace element in living organisms. However, a high level of iron in water results in a bitter taste, color change, and odor in water. Overdose of iron in humans can lead to depression, respiratory issues, convulsions, and cardiac failure (Ghosh et al., 2020). It can also lead to aesthetic issues such as metallic taste, and staining of plumbing fixtures, laundry, and surfaces.

The iron records range from 0.12 mg/l at site number 1 as the lowest to 1 mg/l as the highest at site number 10. With a mean value of 0.43mg/l and a standard deviation of 0.31. About 60 % of the site exceeded the WHO permissible limit of 0.3 mg/l which is an indication of the geology formation of the study site as brown ferruginous quartz sandstone (Healey, 2014; <https://www.mope.gm/geology>) and flood impact during runoff.

Bacteriological parameters

The bacteriological parameter determined in this

study is fecal coliforms. The analysis is done by membrane filtration technique using 100 ml of samples from each site separately and incubating for 18 hours at 44 degrees Celsius. The results of the colonies count showed the presence of fecal coliforms in 9 samples out of 12. Only samples from site1, site2, and site12 record zero growth or not detectable. Adhering to the WHO permissible limit for fecal coliform in drinking water, which is zero (0) or not detectable, 75 % of the samples are unsuitable for drinking purposes because they violated the microbiological safety limit for drinking water quality (Organization, 2004).

Conclusion

This thesis explored the impact of floods on groundwater quality flowing a flash flood event in the study area. The results revealed significant alterations in the physio-chemical and microbial parameters of the groundwater quality following the aftermath of flood events. The WQI indicates 42% of the sample as poor and not fit for consumption before treatment. The physiochemical parameters such as turbidity, and iron exceeded the safe drinking water standards set by the World Health Organization (WHO) in most of the sites. The microbial contamination, indicated by the presence of fecal coliforms in 75% of the total samples, poses serious health risks to humans, particularly in flood-prone areas. The adverse effects of the pollutant with water samples failing to meet the WHO guidelines for potable water were more pronounced in samples from shallow open wells. This deterioration can be attributed to the inundation of wells with floodwaters, which are often contaminated with municipal solid wastes and other refuse.

These findings underscore the importance of regular monitoring of groundwater quality, especially in flood-prone areas, to ensure the safety and suitability of water for drinking and irrigation. It is also crucial to implement proactive measures to protect groundwater sources from contamination and inform community members and policymakers about effective groundwater management strategies.

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Credit Authorship and Contribution Statement

¹Investigation, Data curation, Writing-original draft preparation.

²Supervision, review and editing, Validation.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare that they have no competing or conflicting interests in the work reported in this paper.

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